

THE DIDACTIC EXPLORATION OF A TOY

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Abstract

This communication describes an investigative teaching strategy based on the exploration of a *toy*: a little plane. This is hung from the ceiling by means of a suction cup and has an internal battery to cause the rotation of a propeller. With the propeller turning and the plane away from its equilibrium position, when subjected to an appropriate short pulse, it soon starts to rotate horizontally. The practically stationary motion reached by the aircraft can be considered circular and uniform because it achieves a situation in which the forces acting in the plane have a centripetal resultant. With this little plane moving round it was possible to run a theoretical-experimental lesson with 1st year University students having two major objectives: (i) A theoretical goal which is to review and deepen the knowledge about some concepts and laws of physics. (ii) A practical goal that is to get students to learn how to make the gathering and processing of experimental data and the statistical analysis of errors. It will be made also some brief remarks about the didactic approach and the classroom environment in order to provide a meaningful assimilation of knowledge and that it would please the students, as at the end was manifested by them in a written critical analysis that each of them produced.

Keywords: constructivist learning strategy, meaningful learning, research projects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The plane-toy flying

This work describes a teaching strategy based on an *investigative project*. To facilitate the *meaningful learning*, this strategy is based on a *constructivist epistemology* surpassing the antitheses regarding the relationship between the subject and the object/event. This is the epistemology that underlies the *theory of education* of J. D. Novak [6] and the model of teaching-learning of D. B. Gowin [2], who I am advocating for years. We believe that knowledge, whatever it may be, is constructed based on a complex interaction between a *conceptual* component and another that is *experimental-methodological-computational*, that is, an interaction between *thinking* and *action*. Such construction is based on the research of objects / events, with a focus on fundamental issues about them, translated into focus-questions.

In addition to the *objects / events* and *problems* to investigate about these, it is decisive the interaction that occurs between the *beliefs* of the researchers translated into a *global vision* and an *epistemology*, *theories* and *principles* that underpin the dominated *concepts* and *records* that are gathered with factual validity, as well as the *transformations* of these, because it is based on the *interaction* between all these epistemological elements that are extracted *new meanings*, translated into two kinds of claims: the *cognitive claims* that respond to the questions and the *value claims*, resulting from the analysis of all the work.

2 THE FOCUS- QUESTIONS

How to determine the speed of a plane-pendulum based on the measurement of only two lengths and the knowledge of the gravity acceleration? *What is that speed* in a concrete experiment?

3 WORLD VIEW

Physics, when applied in an explicit way to real objects, becomes more interesting and prepares students for *meaningful learning*.

Meaningful learning *requires effort*, but that effort can be motivated by a *pleasant learning environment* that the allure of toys can cause.

Moreover, simple and transparent experiments, even leading to little accurate results, are richer in terms of meaningful learning than complex experiences with sophisticated materials which lead to results of greater accuracy.

4 UNDERLYING EPISTEMOLOGY

In this work, the nature and validity of knowledge production are seen in a *constructivist perspective* that is *no radical*. Joseph Novak and his followers call it *human constructivism* [5], [8].

5 BASIC PRINCIPLES

The basic principles of this work are the ones that were established by Galileo, Descartes and Newton, with the following current and appropriate statements [7]:

- *Principle of inertia* - There are frames of reference, called inertial frames reference, where the bodies acted upon by outside forces in equilibrium keep steady their speed.

- *Action-reaction principle* - When a body A exerts a force on another body B, this body B exerts a symmetric force on body A.

- *Fundamental principle of dynamics*- The acceleration of a particle is directly proportional to the

resultant of all the forces acting on the particle and inversely proportional to its mass: $\vec{a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \vec{F}_i}{m}$

6 THEORY AND CONCEPTS

From the cognitive point of view, it is important that learners have already studied the basic theory of mechanics and could be minimally aware of the meaning of various magnitudes that will be involved in this work. On the other hand, the very activity itself, when based on a script that includes timely well-formulated questions, is an excellent opportunity to review and deepen the meanings of basic concepts already studied. It is crucial, for example, that students understand why, under what conditions and how the plane can be reduced to the condition of a *particle*. In principle, a plane is a *deformable solid* and in this manner must be considered when, for example, we wish to study the internal stresses in their wings structure caused by turbulence. But in this case, as indeed is the case with transport aircraft in flight, it can be considered a *rigid body* and go further and consider a *second model*, the *particle*. Let us consider the plane reduced to a point with mass equal to its mass. Formerly called a *material point* (or *mass point*), a *particle* is a way to legitimately represent an object, whose legitimacy stems from the fact its dimensions are negligible to the description of its movement and to the action of forces on it, as is this case. But what point is this? This point is the *center of mass* of the airplane that has a remarkable property that is translated by the *center of mass law*:

The center of mass of a particle system moves like an imaginary particle situated therein, having the total mass of the system, under the influence of all applied external forces acting on the system:

$$\sum \vec{F}_{ext} = m \cdot \vec{a}_{CM}$$

But *what forces act* on the plane-toy when it moves? The answer to this question depends on the frame of reference. Adopting an inertial frame of reference, the external forces acting on the plane are:

1 - The *gravitational force* \vec{F}_{grav} whose intensity is the product of the plane mass by the local acceleration of gravity, $F_{grav} = m_{avi} \cdot g$

2 - The *tension force* \vec{F}_{tens} that is the force exerted by the rope on the plane whose direction is along the rope.

3 – The *propulsion force* \vec{F}_{prop} which is a repulsive reaction force on the propeller that is symmetrical to the force exerted by the propeller on the air and causes this is projected backwards.

4 – The *air resistance* \vec{F}_{res} (called drag in fluid dynamics) which is the force that acts in the plane in the instantaneous direction of the motion. In general, this force has a dual origin. An origin is the air friction acting tangentially to the surface of the bodies which move on it, because the air has a certain viscosity. Another origin is the air compressing ahead of the bodies that move on it, together with the drop in pressure in the groove behind them. At high speeds vortices are formed behind the vehicle. When the speed is below 1 m/s (3,6 km/h), F_{res} is primarily due to frictional forces and is directly proportional to velocity. At high speeds, exceeding 36 km/h, the vehicle shape becomes important because the second cause becomes the fundamental, passing F_{res} to be directly proportional to the square of the speed. Finally, at intermediate speeds at which the two causes overlap and are both important, it follows that $F_{res} = bv + cv^2$. The constants b and c depend on the fluid where the object moves; b is expressed in kg/s and the SI unit of c is kg/m.

5 – The *lift force*, \vec{F}_{asc} , which can be considered the sum of two forces. One of them is the *buoyancy of Arquimedes*, which value is given by $F_{imp} = m_{ar\ desl} \times \rho_{ar}$ (ρ_{ar} is the air density). The other is the *aerodynamic lift* caused by air in the displacement plane. Note that in this respect there are two interpretations. The classical one is based on the Bernoulli's law and is incorret. Nowadays we adopt another interpretation based on the action-reaction principle. When the plane flies, the airstream is deflected downward by the wings, what means that the wings exert forces downward on the airstream. According to the action-reaction principle, the airstream exerts symmetrical forces on de wings, then upward which vertical resultant is the aerodynamic lift force.

Taking into account all these forces acting on the plane and the center of mass law we have:

$$\vec{F}_{prop} + \vec{F}_{res} + \vec{F}_{grav} + \vec{F}_{tens} + \vec{F}_{ascenc} = m\vec{a}_{CM}$$

7 GATHERING AND PROCESSING OF DATA

The *data* that students have to collect are as follows, in which the values presented here are *real examples* that have been collected by a student:

Plane mass: $m_{avi} = 38 \text{ g}$

Plane volume: $V_{avi} = 125 \text{ cm}^3$

Length of suspension thread, l/m

Height of the suspension point, h/m
(in the horizontal plane of movement)

l/m		l/m	$(l_i - l)/m$	$(l_i - l)^2/m^2$	h_i/m		h/m	$(h_i - h)/m$	$(h_i - h)^2/m^2$
l_1/m	1,103		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_1/m	0,899		- 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_2/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_2/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}
l_3/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_3/m	0,901		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_4/m	1,100		- 0,02	4×10^{-4}	h_4/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}
l_5/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_5/m	0,898		- 0,02	4×10^{-4}
l_6/m	1,101		- 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_6/m	0,901		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_7/m	1,101		- 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_7/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}
l_8/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_8/m	0,902		+ 0,02	0×10^{-4}
l_9/m	1,103		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_9/m	0,901		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_{10}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{10}/m	0,903		+ 0,03	9×10^{-4}
l_{11}/m	1,104		+ 0,02	4×10^{-4}	h_{11}/m	0,901		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_{12}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{12}/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}

l_{13}/m	1,102	1,102	0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{13}/m	0,899	0,900	- 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_{14}/m	1,101		- 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_{14}/m	0,902		+ 0,02	4×10^{-4}
l_{15}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{15}/m	0,898		- 0,02	4×10^{-4}
l_{16}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{16}/m	0,897		- 0,03	9×10^{-4}
l_{17}/m	1,103		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_{17}/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}
l_{18}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{18}/m	0,900		0,00	0×10^{-4}
l_{19}/m	1,102		0,00	0×10^{-4}	h_{19}/m	0,899		- 0,01	1×10^{-4}
l_{20}/m	1,103		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}	h_{20}/m	0,901		+ 0,01	1×10^{-4}

Students are challenged to *analyze the forces* and check if there are some of them that may be neglected in order to *simplify the treatment of the problem*. This is the case of the lift force, that is the sum of two, the buoyancy of Archimedes and the aerodynamic lift caused by the displacement of the plane in the air. Observing that the plane, after reaching a steady plan, horizontal, circular and uniform motion, the students should immediately infer that these vertical forces can no longer be taken into account because the vertical component of the resultant must be null. But nonetheless, may be challenged to determine the buoyancy of Archimedes and show that it is negligible compared to the gravitational force on the plane.

$$m_{avi} = 38 \text{ g} \Rightarrow \mathbf{F_{grav}} = 0,038 \text{ kg} \times 9,8 \text{ m/s}^2 = \mathbf{0,37 \text{ N}}$$

$$V_{avi} = 125 \text{ cm}^3 \Rightarrow m_{ar \text{ desl}} = 125 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \Rightarrow \mathbf{F_{imp}} = 125 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \times 1,225 \text{ kg/m}^3 = \mathbf{1,5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}}$$

They must analyze the source of the driving force, the increasing of the air resistance (drag) with the plane velocity and conclude that it reaches (in fact very rapidly, as shown by the observation of experiment) a terminal velocity in which the driving force and air resistance can be considered instantaneously balanced, resting an horizontal component of the tension force of the wire which ultimately cause the resulting force). The expression of the fundamental law of center of mass,

$$\vec{F}_{prop} + \vec{F}_{res} + \vec{F}_{grav} + \vec{F}_{tens} + \vec{F}_{ascenc} = m\vec{a}_{CM}$$

can be reduced to

$$\vec{F}_{grav} + \vec{F}_{tens} = m\vec{a}$$

Students should represent the *diagram of forces* acting on the *conical pendulum*, which is the physical model to which the plane motion was reduced. In the inertial frame can be represented by picture beside.

The *resultant of forces* (correct name, unlike resultant force, because it is no longer a force, but rather the sum of the forces) is centripetal.

Using the *Newton's second law of motion*, students, if necessary with the help of the teacher, must demonstrate that the rotation speed of the conical pendulum constituted by the particle plane, can be obtained by the expression

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{g}{h}(l^2 - h^2)} \quad [7]$$

Determining the *mean values* of l and h based on the data collected and considering the normal acceleration of gravity, which is acceptable in the experiment place (situated at sea level and with latitude not too high or low), it was obtained for the *plane speed* the value

$$v = 2,086 \text{ m/s} \rightarrow v = 2,1 \text{ m/s}$$

8 COGNITIVE CLAIMS

The *cognitive claims* are, according to Gowin, the assumed answers to the *focus-questions* that were:

How to determine the speed of a plane-pendulum based on the measurement of only two lengths and the knowledge of the gravity acceleration? What is that speed in a concrete experiment?

Determining the *mean* l/m for the length of the suspension thread, l/m , and the mean h/m for the depth at which the aircraft flew for the suspension point, through the function $v = \sqrt{\frac{g}{h}(l^2 - h^2)}$ we concluded, under the experiment conditions, that the plane flew at a speed of 2.1 m / s.

9 VALUE CLAIMS

All the good experiment must finished with some *comments*, *critics* and *suggestions* about the experiment itself and the obtained results, amongst other considerations. Here are some of them:

- The exploration of toys and games to teach physics is a way of motivating students to become interested in physics and learn it more meaningfully.

- The speed value is variable. The battery had already a relatively low potential, but If the battery voltage was larger, the propulsive force would be greater and plane stationary motion would come about at a higher height measured from the room floor, so a relatively shallow depth h to the point of suspension. The above formula clearly shows that when the subtractive divisor h^2 and the divisor h are smaller, speed is greater, since g and l are constants.

- If it is true that the gravitational force is one of the important forces that act in the plane and depends on its mass, *why the plane speed do not depend on mass* (the magnitude mass is not included in the speed expression)? This is a good question for students to discuss, but before it is necessary they have some «subsumers», concretely the existence of two masses, conceptually different in the classical physics, the inertial mass and the gravitational mass. They have always the same value for the same body, but this equality is a purely experimental fact, is what is called a truth in fact, has no rational basis (even in the relativistic physics it is a postulate, that is accepted by the remarkable confirmation of its consequences). If students have previously assimilated meaningfully this identity between the two masses, then they may develop the next logical reasoning:

- The resultant of forces is proportional to the gravitational force that acts on the plane, and given by the expression $m_i g \cdot \text{tg } \theta$, so that resultant is directly proportional to the gravitational mass of the plane; consequently the gravitational mass contributes indirectly to the plane acceleration.

- In turn, the acceleration, is given by the quotient of this resultant by the inertial mass, $a = \frac{m_g g \cdot \text{tg } \theta}{m_i}$, then is inversely proportional to the inertial mass; consequently, inertial mass is contrary to the acceleration.

- As gravitational mass and inertial mass are equivalent, mass increasing contributes both to increased acceleration (gravitational) and to a lesser acceleration (inertia), so its effect does not count to the acceleration.

9.1 The study of uncertainties

It is important that students perform a *study and evaluation of uncertainties* in this experiment and, based on its conclusions, formulate some value claims. I'll finish this work with this theme, explaining here, in a generic way, the most current and adequate statistical treatment that students should develop whenever opportunities arise like in this project.

Statistics is a science that involves populations or samples with large numbers of elements. In this case, the samples of a length and a height contain 20 measured values for each of them that will be subjected to random errors. As in the vast majority of scientific experiments, the measured values in this work, l_i and h_i , float around mean values, that we consider the *best estimates*, in consequence of the *random*, *statistical* or *accidental* errors. The other kind of errors, *systematic errors*, must be

avoided, as affect all measurements in the same way introducing a systematic error in the final result. Using a ruler very well calibrated to measure these lengths, and adopting a position directly in front of the scale to avoid parallax errors, it is possible avoid the systematic errors.

The *statistical treatment of errors and uncertainties* of a physical magnitude X which is usually made presupposes that we have approximately a *normal* or *Gaussian distribution* of the measured values of that magnitude X . Contrary to what is usual made in our schools, the first step is then confirm that the distributions of values obtained for l and h are approximately normal or Gaussian.

For each of the two distributions (l_i and h_i), students must begin by obtaining the mean and the standard error of mean, that in metrology is designated by experimental standard deviation.

The mean of a distribution of values X_i is given by the expression

$$X = \frac{X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_i + \dots + X_N}{N} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N X_i}{N}$$

The means are in the data table and are, in this practical study:

$$l = 1,102 \text{ m} \quad \text{and} \quad h = 0,900 \text{ m}$$

These *means* and the *measured values* are used to determine the *deviations* ($X_i - X$) between each of the sample values and the mean. They are shown in the table In the table are also shown the squares of the deviations, that must be used to calculate a measure of the dispersion of the measured values around the mean named experimental standard deviation. It is obtained by the expression:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i (X_i - X)^2}{N - 1}}$$

As said, only to a distribution of values that is close of a normal distribution the treatment of uncertainties that is being developed here (different of the one that traditionally is taught in Portuguese secondary schools) has foundation to be applied. To confirm that a distribution of a sufficiently large number of measured values is more or less close to a *normal distribution*, a good process is based in the determination of four descriptive statistics known as *moments* (term originates in mechanics):

$$\text{First moment: } m_1 = \frac{\sum (X_i - X)}{N} = 0 \quad \text{Second moment: } m_2 = \frac{\sum (X_i - X)^2}{N} = \frac{N-1}{N} s^2$$

$$\text{Third moment: } m_3 = \frac{\sum (X_i - X)^3}{N} \quad \text{Fourth moment: } m_4 = \frac{\sum (X_i - X)^4}{N}$$

With these moments about the mean, it becomes possible to obtain the *skewness* and the *kurtosis*. These two measures, together, give us an *idea* of the *distribution shape*.

The *skewness* is related with the more or less symmetry or asymmetry of the distribution. When a distribution (or any set of numbers) is symmetrical, the sum of deviations above of mean, when raised to the third power, will balance the sum of deviations below the mean, when raised to the third power. The skewness expression is

$$g_1 = \frac{m_3}{m_2 \sqrt{m_2}}$$

and when the distribution is symmetrical $m_3 = 0$ and $g_1 = 0$

The concept of *kurtosis* is closely linked to the relative thickness of the tales of distributions, and also is related with the fact that one distribution may be flatter or more peaked than another. The kurtosis expression is

$$g_2 = \frac{m_4}{m_2^2} - 3$$

For the normal distribution, $g_1 = g_2 = 0$ and a distribution will be as more closed to a normal distribution as asymmetry and kurtosis are close to zero.

It is acceptable that the distribution is *slightly asymmetrical, positively skewed* (g_1 slightly larger than 0), when the larger frequencies tend slightly to be concentrated toward the low end and the smaller frequencies toward the high end, or *negatively skewed* (g_1 slightly smaller than 0), when the larger frequencies tend slightly to be concentrated toward the high end and the smaller frequencies toward the low end (g_1 slightly smaller than 0).

In the present case, the moments of l and h necessary to calculate the skewness and the kurtosis are:

$$m_2(l) = 7,5 \times 10^{-5} \quad m_3(l) = -5 \times 10^{-5} \quad m_4(l) = 6,5 \times 10^{-9}$$

$$m_2(h) = 1,9 \times 10^{-4} \quad m_3(h) = 1,45 \times 10^{-6} \quad m_4(h) = 1,1 \times 10^{-8}$$

With these moments it was possible calculate:

- the skewness and kurtosis of the l distribution: $g_1(l) = -0,08$; $g_2(l) = -1,85$
- the skewness and kurtosis of the h distribution: $g_1(h) = 0,55$; $g_2(h) = -2,70$

Although both distributions are slightly *platykurtic*, kurtosis and skewness are close to zero and is justifiable to follow the treatment recommended by GUM [3] that leads to the values of measured quantities directly, l and h , and the value of the quantity measured indirectly, v .

9.1.1 The uncertainties of the direct measurements of l and h

For the direct measurements of the length l and the height h the procedure is as follows:

- With a sufficiently large number of measured values (X_i) for each of the measurands, obtained under the same conditions, with a good guarantee of negligible systematic errors, the *means* of l and h have been determined: $l = 1,102$ m and $h = 0,900$ m
- The *means* and the *measured values* were used to determine the *deviations* ($X_i - X$) about the mean and the *squares* of these *deviations*. They are shown in the table.
- Now the *squares* of the *deviations* are used to calculate the *experimental standard deviation*, the positive square root of the *variance*, a fundamental quantity that expresses the random variations of the observations, and estimates the variance of the probability distribution

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i (X_i - X)^2}{N-1}}$$

The standard deviation is more convenient in practice than the variance because it has the same dimension as the measurand. Using the table values, the following *experimental standard deviations* were obtained: $s_l = 0,00888$ m and $s_h = 0,01414$ m.

- With the experimental standard deviation is easy to obtain the *standard error of the mean*. This value for an *indefinitely large population* (the measured values are only a *little sample* of an indefinitely large population of possible values) is estimated by the formula

$$s_{\bar{x}} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{N}}$$

This standard error of the mean is used in the so called *Type A evaluation of standard uncertainty*, statistically obtained from repeated observations (unlike the Type B evaluation of standard uncertainty, resultant of scientific judgment based on available information as previous measurement data, specifications and so on). The *standard uncertainty of a measurement*, is given by the expression

$$u(X) = \frac{s}{\sqrt{N}}$$

The obtained values were: $u(l) = 0,00200$ m and $u(h) = 0,00316$ m

It is now possible to construct a table with the important values:

Measurands	Means considered as the best estimates	Standard uncertainties
<i>l</i>	1,102 m	0,002 m
<i>h</i>	0,900 m	0,003 m

Finally it is now possible to express the results of the direct measurements. The correct way to state the result of any measurement is, for the measurer, to give his best estimate of the quantity concerned and the range within which he is confident it lies: *best estimate ± uncertainty*

As a matter of fact, there is a certain probability that the value of *X* (whether *l* or *h*) is in the range

$$[X - k_p u, X + k_p u]$$

where $k_p u$ is called the expanded uncertainty for the distribution, the product of the uncertainty by an expansion factor, k_p associated with the level of confidence p . This expanded uncertainty defines an interval about the result of a measurement that may be expected to encompass a large fraction of the distribution of values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand (GUM, 2008, p. 3).

When the distribution is close of the normal distribution, considering that $k_p = 1$, there is a coverage probability or level of confidence of about 68% of the measurand value being in the interval

$$[X - u, X + u]$$

As the distributions of *l* values and *h* values are close normal distributions, there is a confidence level of about 68 % of *l* being between 1,100 m and 1,104 m, what is expressed by $l = 1,102 \text{ m} \pm 0,002 \text{ m}$

and there is a confidence level of about 68 % of *h* being between 0,897 m and 0,903 m, what is expressed by $h = 0,900 \text{ m} \pm 0,003 \text{ m}$

If expanded uncertainty for the distribution is $U = 2u$ ($k_p = 2$), there is a coverage probability or level of confidence of about 96% of the measurand value being in the interval

$$[X - 2 u, X + 2 u]$$

The conclusion is that assuming the expanded uncertainties

$$U_l = 2 \times 0,002 \text{ m} = 0,004 \text{ m} \quad \text{and} \quad U_h = 2 \times 0,003 \text{ m} = 0,006 \text{ m}$$

we have larger intervals, but the coverage probability or level of confidence is more acceptable: about 96%.

These are the uncertainties that were assumed in the rest of the work.

9.1.2 The uncertainty of the indirect measurement of *v*

Accepting as best estimates of *l* and *h* their means, 1,102 m and 0,900 m, we have the following values of the measurands *l* and *h*: $l = 1,102 \text{ m}$ and $h = 0,900 \text{ m}$

Pretending a level of confidence of about 96%, the expanded uncertainties of the length *l* and the height *h*, are: $U_l = 0,004 \text{ m}$ and $U_h = 0,006 \text{ m}$.

We have then the following measurement results:

$$l = 1,102 \text{ m} \pm 0,004 \text{ m} \quad \text{and} \quad h = 0,900 \text{ m} \pm 0,006 \text{ m}$$

The value of the speed is now calculated with the expression

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{g}{h}(l^2 - h^2)}$$

and the obtained value is

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{9,80 \text{ m.s}^{-2}}{0,900 \text{ m}}(1,102^2 - 0,900^2)} \text{ m}^2 = 2,098 \text{ m/s}$$

The question that arises now is: how determine the uncertainty of the plane speed, v , indirectly measured, through the expression. It is the important question of *error propagation*.

The *expression of speed* is of type $S = A^m \times B^n$, with $v = S$, $A = g/h$, $B = l^2 - h^2$ and $m = n = 1/2$.

When the quantity S is a *product or quotient of powers of two quantities A and B*, as in this case, its uncertainty determination is based on the expression:

$$\left(\frac{U_S}{S}\right)^2 = m^2 \left(\frac{U_A}{A}\right)^2 + n^2 \left(\frac{U_B}{B}\right)^2$$

Substituting the values, come:

$$\left(\frac{U_v}{v}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{U_{g/h}}{g/h}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{U_{l^2-h^2}}{l^2-h^2}\right)^2$$

This expression contains the *relative uncertainty* of g/h , and it is necessary to particularize the general expression presented before, with the exponents $m = n = 1$, as follows

$$\left(\frac{U_{g/h}}{g/h}\right)^2 = 0 + \left(\frac{U_h}{h}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{0,006 \text{ m}}{0,900 \text{ m}}\right)^2 = 4,44 \times 10^{-5}$$

as the uncertainty of g is considered zero.

It is now necessary calculate the *uncertainty of a difference*, $U_{l^2-h^2}$ and the *uncertainty of a sum or difference* $S = X \pm Y$ is given by the expression $U_S^2 = U_X^2 + U_Y^2$. In this case we have

$$U_{l^2-h^2}^2 = U_{l^2}^2 + U_{h^2}^2$$

In this expression there are the squared quantities l^2 and h^2 , and it is necessary to particularize once more the general expression to determine U_{l^2} and U_{h^2} as follows:

$$\left(\frac{U_{l^2}}{l^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{U_l}{l}\right)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{U_{h^2}}{h^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{U_h}{h}\right)^2$$

Using these last expressions, we have

$$\left(\frac{U_{l^2}}{l^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{U_l}{l}\right)^2 \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{U_{l^2}}{1,102^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{0,004}{1,102}\right)^2 \Rightarrow U_{l^2} = 0,00881 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\left(\frac{U_{h^2}}{h^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{U_h}{h}\right)^2 \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{U_{h^2}}{0,900^2}\right)^2 = 2^2 \left(\frac{0,006}{0,900}\right)^2 \Rightarrow U_{h^2} = 0,00540 \text{ m}^2$$

Now can be determined $U_{l^2-h^2}^2$: $U_{l^2-h^2}^2 = U_{l^2}^2 + U_{h^2}^2 = 0,00881 \text{ m}^2 + 0,00540 \text{ m}^2 = 0,01421 \text{ m}^2$

And, to obtain U_v , can be used the expression $\left(\frac{U_v}{v}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{U_{g/h}}{g/h}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{U_{l^2-h^2}}{l^2-h^2}\right)^2$

We obtain $\left(\frac{U_v}{v}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4} \times 4,44 \times 10^{-5} + \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{0,0142}{(1,102^2 - 0,900^2)^2} = 1,11 \times 10^{-5} + 2,17 \times 10^{-2}$

to conclude that the *uncertainty in the difference between the squares of the two lengths is what determines the speed uncertainty*, because from the two parts of the sum, the first is negligible compared to the second. This is general, when we have to subtract two approximate quantities.

The relative uncertainty of speed is, then, 0,1473 and the uncertainty is 0,309 m/s.

The plane velocity in this experiment was then

$$(2,098 \pm 0,309) \text{ m/s}$$

Considering as *significant figures* all the exact figures and the first that is approximated, and defining as approximated figures those for which is assigned an uncertainty not less than 1 unit of the same decimal order, we respect this rule: the last significant figure in the result of a measurement is of the same order (in the same decimal position) of the first figure not less than 1 in the uncertainty.

The speed of the plane, expressed in significant figures and with the respective uncertainty, is then:

$$(2,1 \pm 0,3) \text{ m/s}$$

10 FINAL SYNTHESIS

This communication shows how it can be explored a simple plane-toy to adopt a constructivist strategy whose purpose is to facilitate the meaningful learning of important theoretical and experimental knowledge. The strategy is based on a project in which theory and experiment are intertwined. The project is based on the learners work, individual and cooperative, but the teacher continues to play a decisive role, not hesitating to expose one or another issue in a form as conceptually transparent as possible, when it is strictly necessary for students to master the fundamental «subsumers» necessary to learn meaningfully.

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